

Welcome Your New AI Teammate: On Safety Analysis by Leashing Large Language Models (Supplementary Materials)

I. RESULTS OF LLM-BASED HARA

Fig. 1 presents a random sample of the results of a HARA, for a mock driving function, done by an LLM (GPT-4.0) without human intervention. Detailed explanation on the process to generate the HARA and the function, are in the publication.

ID	Guideword	Hazard	Detailed scenario	Hazardous event	Severity	Severity rationale	Safety Goal
17	Commission	CAEM produces a lateral motion request when there is no hazardous collision object in the vicinity.	"Sharp downhill curve with low friction and a bicycle riding in the same direction"	"CAEM produces a lateral motion request causing the vehicle to swerve unnecessarily, potentially causing a collision with the bicycle"	S2	The hazardous event involves a potential collision with a bicycle due to an unnecessary swerve caused by CAEM. Given the nature of the event, the cyclist is an unprotected road user and is at a high risk of severe and life-threatening injuries, especially if the vehicle is moving at a high speed.	Safety Goal: The CAEM system shall avoid producing a lateral motion request unless a hazardous collision object is detected in the vehicle's vicinity.
22	Omission	CAEM fails to produce a lateral motion request when it is necessary to avoid a collision.	"Sharp downhill curve with low friction due to wet road conditions and a pedestrian crossing"	"CAEM fails to produce a lateral motion request causing the vehicle to collide with the pedestrian"	S3	The hazardous event involves a failure in the CAEM, leading to a collision with a pedestrian. Given the unprotected nature of pedestrians and the potential high impact speed, this could result in life-threatening ...	Safety Goal: The CAEM system shall always generate a lateral motion request when necessary to prevent a collision with a pedestrian.
23	Omission	CAEM fails to produce a lateral motion request when it is necessary to avoid a collision.	"Sharp downhill curve with low friction due to wet road conditions and a car parked on the side"	"CAEM fails to produce a lateral motion request causing the vehicle to collide with the parked car"	S1	The CAEM failure causing the vehicle to collide with a parked car would most likely result in light to moderate injuries. This is because the impact speed would be relatively low given that the vehicle is not being ...	Safety Goal: The CAEM system shall always produce a lateral motion request when necessary to avoid any potential collisions.
25	Omission	CAEM fails to produce a lateral motion request when it is necessary to avoid a collision.	"Sharp downhill curve with low friction due to wet road conditions and debris on the road"	"CAEM fails to produce a lateral motion request causing the vehicle to collide with the debris"	S1	The severity of the hazardous event where "CAEM fails to produce a lateral motion request causing the vehicle to collide with the debris" is predicted as S1. This is because, as per the provided severity classes,...	Safety Goal: The Collision Avoidance by Evasive Maneuvers system shall always generate a lateral motion request when a collision is predicted and avoidable.
50	Commission	CAEM produces a lateral motion request when there is no hazardous collision object in the vicinity.	"Intersection with stop signs, a truck approaching from the left"	"CAEM produces a lateral motion request causing the vehicle to swerve into the path of the truck"	S3	The severity of the hazardous event is predicted as S3 due to the high potential for life-threatening injuries or fatal injuries. The CAEM's lateral motion request causing the vehicle to swerve into the path of the truck could...	Safety Goal: The Collision Avoidance by Evasive Maneuvers system shall only produce a lateral motion request when a hazardous collision object is detected, to prevent unnecessary swerving into the path of other vehicles.
51	Commission	CAEM produces a lateral motion request when there is no hazardous collision object in the vicinity.	"Intersection with stop signs, debris on the road"	"CAEM produces a lateral motion request causing the vehicle to swerve unnecessarily"	S1	The hazardous event involves CAEM producing a lateral motion request causing the vehicle to swerve unnecessarily. Considering the nature of the event, the severity is likely to be S1 as it may result in light ...	Safety Goal: The CAEM system shall only produce a lateral motion request when a hazardous collision object is detected in the vehicle's vicinity to avoid unnecessary swerving
77	Omission	CAEM fails to produce a lateral motion request when it is necessary to avoid a collision.	"Transiting an underpass on a wet multi-lane curved road with low friction, a cyclist suddenly crosses"	"CAEM fails to produce a lateral motion request causing a collision with the cyclist"	S2	The severity of the accident is predicted as S2 because the CAEM failing to produce a lateral motion request would likely result in a collision with a cyclist, an unprotected road user. Given the nature of the ac...	Safety Goal: The CAEM system shall always generate a lateral motion request when a collision with a cyclist is predicted and unavoidable, to enforce collision avoidance.
91	Commission	CAEM produces a lateral motion request when there is no hazardous collision object in the vicinity.	"Transitioning from a bridge to a sharp uphill curve with a solid line marking and a pedestrian is crossing the road"	"CAEM produces a lateral motion request causing the vehicle to swerve towards the pedestrian"	S3	The hazardous event involves a vehicle swerving towards a pedestrian, which is an unprotected road user. Given the sudden lateral motion request produced by CAEM, the impact speed could be high. This scenario may...	Safety Goal: The Collision Avoidance by Evasive Maneuvers system shall avoid producing a lateral motion request unless a hazardous collision object is detected in the vehicle's vicinity.
196	Omission	CAEM fails to produce a lateral motion request when it is necessary to avoid a collision.	"Scenario: A car from the opposite direction crosses into the ego vehicle's lane"	"Hazardous Event: CAEM fails to produce a lateral motion request, leading to a potential collision with the oncoming car"	S2	The CAEM failure to produce a lateral motion request could lead to a collision with the oncoming car. Given the potential for a front collision at a potentially high speed, severe and life threatening injuries are probable ...	Safety Goal: The CAEM system shall always produce a lateral motion request when necessary to avoid any potential collision with an oncoming car.

Fig. 1. Presents part of the LLM-based HARA without human intervention. The complete list will be made available as a Supplementary Materials [removed for double blind review]. Please note that the results shown in this figure are generated by an AI tool and is only for the purpose of this research as an illustration. They shall not be used in a real application.